

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL WORK IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article discusses the importance of the preschool education system as the initial link of education in child development, as well as innovative forms and methods of organizing educational work in preschool educational institutions.

Keywords: education, technology, innovation, cluster, graphic organizer, interactive methods.

Introduction. Organization of education of perfect generation has been an important requirement and main goal of social society in all eras. That is why the world community is carrying out extensive reforms to further develop the field of education. As a clear example of this, we can say that UNICEF contributed to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education" approved by the Senate on December 14, 2019. Since 2018, UNICEF has invested almost \$2 million in government support for early childhood education. These investments have resulted in new laws, national policies and plans, data collection and quality assurance mechanisms. It has been. UNICEF also supported the quality of early childhood education by revising the early childhood education curriculum, standards for early learning development and teacher training. Service delivery has been expanded by introducing alternative models and further implementation of digital solutions for children, parents and teachers. As a result of this support, the government was able to provide quality pre-school education to nearly 2 million children between the ages of 3 and 6 by the beginning of 2022.

In our country today, using the experience of developed countries, presidential decisions and decrees on the development of the preschool education system, legal documents are being developed. As a clear proof of this, we can cite President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's decree No. 60 of January 28, 2022 on the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. The 39th goal of this decree emphasizes bringing the quality of education to a new level in the preschool education system, introducing an improved system for improving the professional training and skills of kindergarten employees, more than 160,000 pedagogues in 2022-2026. Improvement of personnel qualification and improvement of pre-school educational processes on the basis of scientifically based approaches were mentioned. Therefore, the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogic and information technologies in the educational process is becoming a need of the hour.

Until now, in traditional preschool education organizations, the goal was to feed the students, feed them and satisfy other similar needs just to pass the time. changed. Today's requirements for preschool education reject this system. The educator creates conditions for the child's development, formation, learning and upbringing in preschool educational institutions, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. Education of children in preschool education organizations on the basis of innovative technologies is of great

importance in achieving high performance. Pedagogical technology and interactive methods ensure that students acquire age-appropriate knowledge, skills and competences. Analysis of literature on the topic. One of the important characteristics of modern education is the achievement of the innovative nature of the pedagogue's activity. In developed foreign countries, the issue of achieving an innovative nature of pedagogue activity has been seriously studied since the 60s of the last century. In particular, H. Barnett, J. Basset, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, R. Carlson, M. Mays, A. Havelock, D. Chen, R. Edem, F. N. Gonobolin, S. M. Godnin, V. I. Zagvyazinsky, V. A. Kalik, In the works carried out by researchers such as N.V. Kuzmina and V.A. Slastenin, innovative activity, innovative approach to pedagogical activity, grounding of innovative ideas and their effective implementation in practice, practical use of them in the activity of a pedagogue by being aware of pedagogical innovations created in foreign countries and in the republic the content of actions is highlighted.

Scientists such as K. Angelovsky, G. I. Gorskaya, V. A. Kan-Kalik, S. I. Kuzmina, V. A. Slastyonin, L. M. Fridman covered the general aspects of innovative activity in their scientific research works. I. Schumpacher and N. Kondratev are considered the first and greatest theoreticians of the concept of innovation. K. Angelovsky, V. A. Slastyonin and V. I. Slobotchikov tried to prove in their scientific research that innovative activity is a special form of pedagogical activity.

In our country, scientific and research work is being carried out on the problems of developing pedagogical innovations. Pedagogical scientists N.Azizkhodjayeva, B.Farbemon, N.Sayidahmedov, K.Zaripov, M.Ochilov, O'.Tolipov, M.Usmonboyeva, M.Jumaniyozova and others can be mentioned.

Research methodology. Innovation (innovation in English) is innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students. Today, as a result of the emergence of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and the idea of renewing the educational process, a new direction in the pedagogical activity of a pedagogue-educator, the concept of "innovative activity of a pedagogue" appeared. Concepts such as innovation in pedagogy, innovative activity, innovative pedagogy, management of innovative processes in education first appeared in the 60s of the 20th century, when the concept of "educational technology" was recognized in the USA and Western European countries. At that time, the Center and Institute of Pedagogical Innovations was established in Europe. As a result of the conducted scientific research, in the second half of the 80s of the last century, a new scientific direction was formed: pedagogical activity is a combination of creative process and pedagogical innovations. This made it possible to analyze the formation and development process of the innovative pedagogical activity of the pedagogue-educator. Innovative activity refers to the creative approach of the teacher to mastering existing forms and tools for improving his profession. It should also be recognized that the scientific ideas and classifications that are stable and acceptable to everyone about innovations in education and innovative pedagogical activity have not been fully formed until now.

Innovation is the use of technology, forms and methods in a certain field of activity or production, a new approach to solving a problem, or the use of a new technological process, which is known to lead to greater success than before. Implementation of innovation is carried out in innovation processes.

Innovative process refers to the process of preparing for and implementing innovative changes. The teacher-educator participates in the creation, application and popularization of

innovation as a subject and organizer of innovative activities. Nowadays, while the attention to education of children of preschool age and their education is increasing day by day, great attention is paid to the innovative skills of educators. Training of educators based on such initiatives and innovations is promising for the development of educational content, and also has a positive effect on the development of the preschool education system.

The main rules of organizing educational work:

- clearly defining the purpose of the work to be done, imagining the action as a whole from the beginning to the end;
- setting specific tasks for each subordinate;
- preparation of all necessary things for the expected work;
- defining certain criteria for determining the results;
- responsibility, its owner and distribution of reporting time;
- providing guidance to executives as a means of organizing the organizational system;

Conducting educational work in preschool education organizations educates the important qualities of the student, and at the same time, it is considered the foundation of his future behavior and habits. For this reason, the employees of the preschool education organization should approach the organization of educational activities with responsibility. In the implementation of this task, interactive methods will help us.

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, and the learner is at the center of the education and training process. The use of such methods in the organization of educational work helps to achieve high efficiency. When choosing interactive methods, the educational goal, the number and opportunities of students, the material conditions of the institution, the pedagogical skills of the educator, etc. are taken into account. Below we present the interactive methods used in the organization of educational work in preschool education.

"Venn diagram" method.

A technique that allows for analysis, synthesis and generalization while comparing two types of things that have different and common characteristics. Two or more intersecting circles are constructed.

For example:

SPRING

FALL

On the left side of the circles, pictures representing the events occurring only in the spring season, on the right side, the pictures representing only the changes in the autumn season, and the pictures representing the characteristics of both the spring and autumn seasons are placed in the middle of the circle.

For example, for the spring season, pictures such as blooming trees, chamomiles, swallows, green valleys, and tulips are placed.

For the autumn season, pictures depicting the yellowing of tree leaves and autumn harvesting processes are selected.

Pictures depicting the process of cloudy and rainy weather are placed at the intersections of the circles, related to both seasons.

The method of "logical tangled chains".

Pictures representing the sequence of events in 5-6 separate fairy tales consisting of a chronological or cause-and-effect chain, such as a sequence of numbers, are placed on a separate piece of paper and placed in confusion.

The group will have to explain how to place the papers with this writing in the correct sequence. After the trainees have placed them, the trainer should check whether the group's assumptions are correct or incorrect.

"Corners" method.

The "Corners" method is a cooperative learning activity aimed at organizing a discussion. When working with this method, listening to a text, a fairy tale or an instructive story of educational value and watching its film screening can be used to solve a problem situation. The organization of this method is very simple and easy.

The rules are as follows:

- ❖ A topic is selected for discussion.
- ❖ The participants are divided into groups on the basis of similar thoughts, views, and attitudes, and they tell each other the arguments and grounds that protect these views and attitudes. The participants of the group speak in turn.
- ❖ Some participants of a group who believe that the arguments of their opponents are valid and strong may change their opinions and join opposing groups. This, in turn, encourages all groups to search for strong evidence and foundations.
- ❖ At the end of the session, conclusions are drawn, and the participants are asked to organize a scene based on their thoughts, views, and attitudes on the topic. This performance will definitely be attended by the teacher. The scene has a positive effect on the child's educational situation, as it is staged on the basis of an instructive story.

"Sinquain" method.

Sinquain is a method that gives the opportunity to briefly describe information, to express complex ideas, feelings, and imaginations with the help of a few words. It requires thoughtful reflection based on a rich reservoir of insights.

"Sinkwein" is a "poem", which requires the synthesis of information and materials in short expressions written or reflected in connection with an event.

The word "cinquain" is a French word that translates as "five", so "cinquain is a poem of five lines".

The rule for writing a syncway is as follows:

When we use this method among the students of the preparatory group in the preschool education organization:

- ❖ in the first line, the topic is written with one word, it is usually chosen by the educator and it is a related word in the noun group;
- ❖ In the second line, the subject should be described with two words. The teacher asks the children to say words that indicate the quality and status of the word spoken in the first line, and chooses 2 suitable words from the words spoken by the children. These words should belong to the category of adjectives.

- ❖ in the third line, actions on this topic are described with three words;
- ❖ in the fourth line, a sentence or phrase containing four words is written indicating the relevance to the topic;
- ❖ the fifth line is a one-word synonym that repeats the essence of the topic.

Syncway in practice: a tool for synthesizing complex information; a tool for assessing the students' concept stock; very useful as a means of creative expression. Syncway is a fast, yet powerful tool for reflecting, synthesizing, and summarizing concepts and information.

Example:

1. Lesson (1 noun)
2. Interesting, meaningful (2 qualities)
3. We read, learn, do (3 verbs)
4. We acquire knowledge, skills, qualifications. (4 sentences or phrases)
5. Training (1 synonym).

Conclusions and suggestions. In raising the future generation as a well-rounded person, the field of preschool education plays an important role as the initial link of education and training. The use of innovative technologies by educators of preschool educational organizations in the process of education is of particular importance. In this case, educators should pay attention to the fact that the technology is compatible with the child's age characteristics, intellectual development potential, and also that these technologies help to develop the child's competencies. The following recommendations were developed for the use of innovative technologies in preschool educational organizations:

- forming the concept of mutual respect in children;
- consideration of children's interests and abilities;
- to create conditions for children's creative and free thinking while avoiding banning and punishment methods;
- preventing noise when using interactive methods;
- taking into account the psychological characteristics of children (attention, perception, emotional states).
- taking into account the individual characteristics of the student when using innovative technologies;
- it is necessary to regularly monitor the effect of the innovative technologies used on the education of the students.

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